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Audio technology for improving social interaction in extended reality

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In recent years, extended reality (XR) has gained interest as a platform for human communication, with the emergence of the “Metaverse” promising to reshape social interactions. At the same time, concerns about harmful behavior and criminal activities in virtual environments have increased. This paper explores the potential of technology to support social harmony within XR, focusing specifically on audio aspects. We introduce the concept of acoustic coherence and discuss why it is crucial for smooth interaction. We further explain the challenges of speech communication in XR, including noise and reverberation, and review sound processing methods to enhance the auditory experience. We also comment on the potential of using virtual reality as a tool for the development and evaluation of audio algorithms aimed at enhancing communication. Finally, we present the results of a pilot study comparing several audio enhancement techniques inside a virtual environment.

KEYWORDS

social interaction, extended reality, virtual acoustic simulation, acoustic matching, speech enhancement

1 Introduction

The idea of XR as a platform for human communication has become increasingly popular in recent years. It has led to the emergence of the concept of the “Metaverse,” which is speculated to become the leading medium of communication in the future (Dzardanova et al., 2022; Dwivedi et al., 2022). The primary aim of such virtual worlds is to enable individuals from different locations to interact within a shared audiovisual environment. In parallel to the widespread appreciation for the technological potential and the promise of fostering social connections, there is also a common concern that the Metaverse could facilitate toxic behavior and pose threats of criminal activity (Gómez-Quintero et al., 2024). In response to this, there has been a growing interest in studying ways in which technology could promote social harmony and inclusive behavior within virtual worlds. In this brief paper, we take a closer look at this issue from the perspective of audio technology. We identify challenges related to speech communication in XR and discuss sound processing methods that could improve the overall auditory experience in XR. We support this discussion with a pilot study featuring virtual reality, spatial sound and selected audio enhancement methods, and report the preliminary results obtained from a user feedback survey.

2 Challenges of speech communication in extended reality

Figure 1A illustrates a common VR meeting scenario where four users, depicted as avatars, gather around a virtual table to engage in a conversation. Because the users are physically located in different spaces, the microphones of their respective headsets, apart from speech, capture additional environment-specific disturbances e.g., noise, background sounds, wind or movement disturbances, and reverberation. Additionally, microphone positioning may not be optimal for capturing voice with high quality (See Figure 1C). The final mixture of sounds delivered to the user originates from several

distinct environments. This results in a virtual scene where the acoustic elements fail to form a coherent and plausible soundscape. *Coherence* in XR refers to the degree to which the virtual environment behaves in a reasonable or predictable way (Collins et al., 2017; Skarbez et al., 2020; Slater, 2009). In this paper, we adopt this concept and use the term *acoustic incoherence* to describe a lack of a plausible auditory illusion in mixed reality—a problem that has already been discussed by several authors (Neidhardt et al., 2022; Fantini et al., 2023; Popp and Murphy, 2024). Acoustic incoherence may arise from the evident contrast between the acoustics of individual sound sources or from the discrepancies between perceived sounds and their visual representations within the

virtual environment. In augmented reality (AR) scenarios (Figure 1B), where remotely recorded sounds must seamlessly integrate with the user's real soundscape, such incoherence might be even more noticeable.

Beyond acoustic incoherence, even in an ideal scenario where all audio sources are perfectly adapted to each user's environment, group conversations in XR can still lead to the so-called "cocktail party effect," where multiple people speak at the same time (Cherry, 1953). This situation is particularly challenging because it involves both energetic and informational masking and requires a high level of selective auditory attention (Brungart et al., 2006; Oberfeld and Klockner-Nowotny, 2016). Below, we explain why difficult acoustic conditions are a potential bottleneck for interactions in XR.

Human interaction heavily relies on auditory perception. Various studies illustrate how factors such as noise, reverberation, and the inaccuracy of binaural cues can impair our ability to understand speech, localize sound sources in space, or concentrate on specific sounds (Puglisi et al., 2021; Good and Gilkey, 1996; Bronkhorst, 2000). Even when the linguistic message is comprehended, reduced audio quality escalates the effort required for listening, resulting in measurable physiological changes in the body, typically associated with psycho-social stressors (Francis and Love, 2020).

The studies mentioned above focus on measuring how sound degradation affects an individual's auditory perception and ability to understand speech. While good hearing and speech comprehension are usually prerequisites for communication, passive listening is not the same as active communication. In recent years, there has been growing interest in measuring how acoustic conditions influence communication between groups of people. New study paradigms aim to quantify conversation quality by analyzing changes in speech production, turn-taking time, or movement synchronization between participants (McKellin et al., 2007; Hadley and Ward, 2021; Beechey et al., 2020; Petersen et al., 2022; Petersen, 2024; Sørensen et al., 2021; Hadley et al., 2019). Generally, factors that degrade speech intelligibility or increase listening effort also impact conversation dynamics. Noisy conditions, in particular, force conversation partners to adapt their behavioral strategies to overcome communication challenges.

The influence of adverse acoustic conditions has also been discussed from a social perspective. In Jones et al. (1981) the authors review the existing evidence and propose three main social effects of noise: (a) social interaction is disrupted by the masking of sounds; (b) the weighting of interpersonal judgments is changed; and (c) noisy settings are perceived as aversive, which governs the utility of social engagement. Moreover, multiple studies report the negative effects of noise exposure on the social interactions in the work environment or classroom (Singh et al., 1982; Cohen and Spacapan, 1978).

Communication difficulties and their psycho-social consequences have also been well studied in the hearing-impaired population - a social group inherently exposed to degraded auditory information (Podury et al., 2023; Monzani et al., 2008). People with hearing difficulties are more at risk of social isolation and depression. They perceive the interactions as less successful, and more frustrating and effortful (Aliakbaryhosseinabadi et al., 2023; Beechey et al., 2020).

The studies mentioned above represent well-established research on the perceptual effects of low signal-to-noise ratios, which are typical in complex, real-world acoustic environments and often studied in the context of hearing impairment. However, sound can influence the overall experience in VR in other ways, such as impacting immersion (Geronazzo et al., 2019; Kim and Lee, 2022) and presence (Rogers et al., 2018; Kern and Ellermeier, 2020). For a recent scoping review, see Bosman et al. (2024). Additionally, a few studies have investigated the auditory consequences of audio-visual incongruities unique to XR, such as their effects on distance perception (Gil-Carvajal et al., 2016), localization (Roßkopf et al., 2023), and speech recognition (Siddig et al., 2019). It is important to note that these aspects, even if they do not directly affect auditory perception, may still be important for successful communication.

In summary, although the influence of audio on social interaction in XR still requires more investigation (Bosman et al., 2024), the existing literature suggests that human interactions are likely to be less harmonious in environments with poor acoustics.

3 Technologies to improve audio interactions

Binaural technology is the foundation for most audio experiences in virtual and augmented reality. Through a rigorous preparation of the signal in the left and right audio channels, an auditory illusion of sound being placed at a specific location inside a defined environment can be created. In an XR meeting scenario, the voice captured by the headset on one user's end becomes a virtual audio source for the other users.

Figure 1D illustrates a possible audio processing pipeline applied to such a recording before reaching the listener's ears: Initially, the sound emitted by User 1 in Environment 1 - s_1e_1 - is captured by the microphones of the headset. Before transmitting the signal to User 2, environmental disturbances degrading the recording must be eliminated through *denoising* and *dereverberation* to obtain the clean source signal s_1 . In parallel, the originally captured signal serves as a source of environmental information e_1 extracted in the *acoustic characterization* step, essential for later adapting the audio received from User 2. Once the recording is cleaned of unwanted disturbances, it can be passed as input to the binaural rendering stage. Binaural rendering involves a) *spatialization*, which creates a perception of a specific direction according to the relative position and orientation between the source and receiver, and b) *acoustic matching*, which applies the acoustic properties of the target room. The exact order of these operations depends on the chosen binaural rendering method (See Gari et al. (2022) for a review). Finally, the spatialized sound with modified room acoustic properties - s_1e_2 - is delivered to the user's ears. It's noteworthy that in VR, as the user moves their head, the relative direction of sound arrival changes, requiring real-time updates of the entire binaural rendering block.

The depicted pipeline specifically addresses augmented reality, where the target acoustic space is defined by the user's actual location. Consequently, the properties of the target environment must be estimated through acoustic characterization. In the graph, the user's own voice recording serves as the source of this information. However, alternative methods exist for estimating room acoustic properties, such as estimating plausible

TABLE 1 Traditional and deep-learning-based approaches for the sub-tasks of virtual acoustic simulation.

Task	Traditional approaches	Deep-learning approaches
Denoising	Virag (1999), Krishnamoorthy and Prasanna (2009)	Yuliani et al. (2021), Pascual et al. (2017)
De-reverberation	Li and Deng (2021), Nakatani et al. (2006)	Ochieng (2023), Su et al. (2020b)
Acoustic characterization	Ratnam et al. (2003), Kendrick et al. (2007), Hua (2002)	Martin et al. (2023), Steinmetz et al. (2021)
Binaural synthesis	Cuevas Rodriguez et al. (2022), Rafaely et al. (2022)	Huang et al. (2022), Lluís et al. (2022), Zhu et al. (2024)
Acoustic matching	Välämäki et al. (2016), Peters et al. (2012)	Koo et al. (2021), Im and Nam (2024), Su et al. (2020a)

reverberation from images (Chen et al., 2022). In VR setups, this step is typically unnecessary since the reverberation can be simulated from scratch using geometric methods based on polygon meshes in the scene (Välämäki et al., 2016).

The sub-tasks depicted in Figure 1D have been the focus of research in audio and acoustics, leading to diverse approaches utilized in a broad range of audio processing devices. Notably, recent advancements in artificial intelligence are beginning to change the landscape of audio technology. Besides numerous deep learning solutions for individual signal processing tasks, there is a trend of replacing entire conventional audio processing pipelines with end-to-end neural approaches. Table 1 presents a non-exhaustive comparison between traditional signal-processing-based solutions and their deep-learning-based counterparts used for solving the challenges of audio in XR.

4 VR as a tool to study the influence of sound on human interactions

In previous sections, we outlined the challenges of interactions in virtual reality (VR) that stem from the insufficient quality of acoustic signals, and we discussed the state-of-the-art audio technologies that can help to mitigate these challenges. In this section, we want to draw the reader's attention to the fact that VR not only benefits from advancements in audio technology but can also serve as a powerful tool for researchers and engineers developing new audio algorithms, particularly in the domain of speech enhancement.

Although most of the speech enhancement algorithms aim at facilitating smooth communication, they are seldom assessed in actual communication settings. Instead, novel algorithms, especially in rapidly evolving fields, are typically evaluated using objective metrics or basic passive listening tests. There are practical reasons for this gap: Setting up an interactive communication scenario in the lab is time-consuming, requires multiple participants, and poses significant challenges in ensuring reproducibility or scaling the study paradigms. VR offers the possibility to simulate real-life environments with highly controlled audio content, visual input and head movements, providing a great platform for detailed testing of speech enhancement algorithms. Additionally, VR can automatically generate large volumes of realistic data samples, which can significantly augment the training and evaluation datasets needed for developing deep learning models.

The idea to use VR to study human interaction, originating from experimental psychology (Pan and Hamilton, 2018), is gaining

interest in hearing research (Mehra et al., 2020; Keidser et al., 2020; Hohmann et al., 2020) and musicology (Van Kerrebroeck et al., 2021). In our opinion, VR is likely to become a core technology in developing audio algorithms aimed at enhancing human communication, particularly for assistive listening devices such as consumer earbuds, hands-free communication headsets, hearing aids, and head-mounted displays for XR.

5 Pilot study

We designed a qualitative pilot experiment to validate the virtual conversation scenes with spatial audio, varying acoustic conditions, and speech enhancement. In this prototype study, users are asked to evaluate aspects of the proposed virtual environment and rate several different speech enhancement algorithms. Below, we describe the technical system, the method for collecting user feedback, and the obtained results.

5.1 VR application

Using Unity game development software, we created an interactive environment simulating a typical meeting in VR, where four people engage in a conversation. The user is virtually placed at the same table as four virtual characters and has the opportunity to observe and listen to their conversation, while also being able to modify audio processing via the user interface (See Figure 1E). The user interface allows switching between the following audio options:

- COHERENT: original recording of the avatars conversation.
- INCOHERENT: noisy, reverberant audio without signal enhancement.
- CONVENTIONAL AUDIO PROCESSING: spectral noise gating (Sudheer Kumar et al., 2023).
- DEEP LEARNING METHOD FROM 2020: Facebook Denoiser (Defossez et al., 2020).
- DEEP LEARNING METHOD FROM 2023: DeepFilterNet (Schröter et al., 2023).

The signal flow of our VR application is depicted in Figure 1F: Each virtual character was assigned to an audio source extracted from a DiPCo dataset containing close microphone recordings of real conversations (Van Segbroeck et al., 2019). The clean audio sources were corrupted with various noises and reverberations to

mimic a real scenario (i.e., each participant located in a different noisy space). The broadband SNR was set to -5 dB for all sources. We used ACE database for room impulse responses (Eaton et al., 2015), AVAD-VR for anechoic recordings of instruments (They and Katz, 2019), and Freesound (Fonseca et al., 2021) for other background sounds. Next, the audio was processed by one (or none) of the signal enhancement methods listed in the user interface. The enhanced audio was spatialized based on the relative position between the source and the listener and placed in a simulated acoustic environment i.e., a shoebox room corresponding to the visual scene. We used the Steam Audio spatializer plugin as the binaural synthesis engine. Apart from spatialization, the signal was processed offline. The offline signal enhancement did not affect the binaural reproduction, thereby not limiting the user's ability to move their head and explore the virtual scene. Nevertheless, it simulated an idealized future scenario where speech enhancement algorithms could process sound in real time without compromising performance. A real VR or AR conversation would require implementing a fully real-time version of these algorithms, which is challenging and still an active field of research (Westhausen et al., 2024). This interactive demonstration was developed as a standalone Meta Quest 2 application.

5.2 Procedure

Using the application described above, we conducted a within-subject experiment with five different acoustic conditions. We invited 11 young participants (age 31–42). Apart from self-reported healthy hearing, there were no other inclusion criteria. All participants volunteered to take part in the study. They were informed in detail about the content of the experiment, agreed to have their survey responses used in the analysis presented here, and were free to withdraw from the demonstration and analysis at any time. No personal information was collected, and only anonymized data was used.

Participants were asked to put on the Quest 2 VR headset coupled with Sennheiser Epos Adapt 360 over-ear headphones. First, they were given an introduction, which consisted of several guided VR scenes. The scenes demonstrated the main audio features in VR and gave examples of acoustically coherent and incoherent scenes in virtual reality. Additionally, a hearing loss simulation by Cuevas-Rodríguez et al. (2019) was presented to raise awareness about auditory perception of individuals with hearing impairments.

After this introduction, the participants were virtually placed in the VR meeting scene (described in detail in the previous subsection), where they could adjust the audio enhancement settings via the user interface. Participants were instructed to consider aspects like speech intelligibility and sound quality. They were encouraged to experiment with audio settings until they formed a clear opinion about each audio processing option. After completing this phase, participants removed the headset and completed an online questionnaire about their experience in the virtual scene. The questionnaire consisted of 7 Likert scale type questions. Likert scales are broadly used in social sciences for the collection of attitudes and opinions (Likert, 1932). They typically consist of 5 options ranging from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree” (or a similar 5-point symmetrical range of responses with

neutral response in the middle) and have been previously used for evaluating soundscapes (Mitchell et al., 2020).

The following questions were presented in the survey:

1. *The listening scenario, i.e., audio material, source positions, loudness levels felt realistic (strongly disagree - strongly agree).*
2. *It was difficult to follow the conversation in the acoustically incoherent scene (strongly disagree - strongly agree).*
3. *I would have difficulty interacting with people in acoustic conditions similar to the acoustically incoherent scene (strongly disagree - strongly agree).*
4. *The experiment has raised my awareness about perception of sound (strongly disagree - strongly agree).*
5. *The experiment has raised my awareness about audio technology (strongly disagree - strongly agree).*
6. *Rate how much each audio processing method helped you understand speech (did not help at all - helped a lot).*
7. *Rate the audio quality provided by each audio processing method (very poor - very good).*

To analyze the responses we used the Mann–Whitney U test. The collected data is ordinal, meaning the response categories have a natural order but potentially unequal intervals between them. This non-parametric test compares the distributions of two independent groups and does not assume normality, making it suitable for analyzing Likert scale data that may not follow a normal distribution.

A video with the full demonstration including the introduction is available online¹.

5.3 Pilot results and discussion

The survey results are shown in Figure 2. In Question 1, most participants agreed that the selected listening scenario was realistic, supporting the expectation that virtual reality can create ecologically valid acoustic scenarios, as proposed by Hohmann et al. (2020) and Mehra et al. (2020).

In Question 2 and 3, participants agreed that the incoherent acoustic scene represented conditions in which it would be difficult to follow the conversation and interact with others. In additional interviews, they reported that the acoustic coherence had a crucial impact on the willingness to take part in the VR meeting and the ability to associate individual voices with the avatars. The result of Question 2 confirms the well-known finding that speech intelligibility is impaired by noise or reverberation (Bradley, 1986; Bronkhorst, 2000). The results for Question 3 suggest that not only speech comprehension, but also interpersonal interactions, are negatively affected by poor acoustics, which is in agreement with the findings of McKellin et al. (2007) and Hadley et al. (2019) who studied real conversations in noisy settings.

Questions 4 and 5 assessed the potential educational impact of participating in the experiment. The results indicate that for most of them, the experiment increased awareness of sound perception and

¹ Video available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SaXMYn8b3eg&t=124s>.

audio technology, although not all participants experienced this benefit.

Questions 6 and 7 rated three speech enhancement methods. While it was evident that all methods improved the auditory experience to some degree, participants reported distinct preferences when evaluating the methods. The survey questions were formulated to gather ratings reflecting speech intelligibility (Question 6) and perceived sound quality (Question 7) for each algorithm. The DNN-based solution by Schröter et al. (2023) was regarded as the most beneficial for understanding speech and yielding the highest signal quality. The second-best option in both categories was the DNN-based method by Defossez et al. (2020). Finally, the conventional speech enhancement technique (Sudheer Kumar et al., 2023) was rated as the least helpful, providing only marginal improvement in speech perception and exhibiting poor audio quality. These results suggest that while traditional signal processing may be insufficient for improving communication in XR, recent deep learning approaches show significant potential.

The benefit of DNN-based techniques over traditional methods has been reported in multiple studies (Xu et al., 2013; Zheng et al., 2023). This benefit is generally attributed to the fact that DNNs do not rely on the unrealistic assumptions about the statistical properties of speech and noise that constrain the performance of traditional methods. However, it should be noted that end-to-end deep learning approaches, such as those used in this pilot study, remain computationally expensive and may be challenging to implement in real-time on mobile devices.

Only a few studies in the context of hearing aid signal enhancement have compared various speech enhancement techniques in complex acoustic environments (Gusó et al., 2023; Westhausen et al., 2024; Hendrikse et al., 2020). Furthermore, most evaluations rely on objective metrics, which have been criticized for providing only a limited view of how humans perceive sound (Torcoli et al., 2021; López-Espejo et al., 2023). To our knowledge, there is no prior research comparing traditional and DNN-based speech enhancement methods subjectively in audio-visual VR.

Although the method by Defossez et al. (2020) received slightly higher ratings than Sudheer Kumar et al. (2023), this difference was not statistically significant in either aspect (see Figure 2, bottom panel). Informal listening reports indicate that while the DNN is better at removing noise, it distorts the signal in a way that makes listening to the conversation unpleasant. This suggests that perceptually distinct signals can result in similar effective speech enhancement and comparable assessed quality. Hence, despite the benefit of SNR, we might expect similar communication benefit. Further studies are needed to quantify how different types of distortions interact with binaural XR environments and if such differences between methods influence social interactions.

Collecting participant opinions is an efficient way to probe perception. In this pilot study, we used this approach to explore new research ideas. However, to validate these findings, future studies will require quantitative measures of communication success.

6 Discussion

In this article, we presented our perspective on how contemporary audio technologies enhance social interaction in extended reality (XR). Our main goal was to conceptually link technical topics in XR and audio technology with concepts from the psychology of human interaction, particularly speech communication and hearing science.

Extensive research in psychology and auditory science shows that sound is fundamental to human communication. However, ideal auditory input is often difficult or impossible to achieve. Whether it's noisy environments encountered in daily life, partially inaudible sounds for individuals with hearing impairments, or remote meetings where sound undergoes multiple modifications before reaching users' ears, imperfect sound can hinder effective communication (Balters et al., 2023; Beechey et al., 2020; Hadley et al., 2019; McKellin et al., 2007).

In this work, we focused on the challenges of achieving ideal audio signals in remote XR meeting scenarios. Beyond well-known issues like background noise and the "cocktail party" effect, XR presents additional challenges, such as incongruences between individual audio sources or between audio and visual virtual representations (Neidhardt et al., 2022). Distortions introduced by the signal processing pipeline, which involves multiple sub-tasks, may result in signals unfamiliar to our ears. Even with perfect hearing, the brain may struggle to adapt quickly to these synthetic sounds (Willmore and King, 2023).

We introduced the concept of "acoustic incoherence" to describe these new audio challenges posed by XR technology and emphasized the importance of coherent acoustic scenes for smooth interaction in XR. We briefly reviewed existing solutions to the sub-tasks of virtual acoustic simulation, mentioning deep-learning-based alternatives to conventional approaches, which are likely to dominate digital audio processing in the near future.

Although it is clear that sound influences interaction, few studies examine this influence in actual interactive settings (McKellin et al., 2007). Similarly, while the ultimate goal of speech enhancement is to improve communication, speech enhancement algorithms are rarely evaluated in interactive communication settings (Keidser et al., 2020). VR provides a valuable platform for creating realistic evaluation scenarios for hearing research and audio algorithm development. We believe that, in the long term, prioritizing communication benefits will transform speech enhancement algorithms into tools that enhance human interactions, enabling users to experience more harmonious social connections.

To support our perspective, we presented a pilot study conducted in virtual reality comparing classical and deep-learning-based approaches to speech enhancement. The results indicate that deep-learning-based methods hold potential for improving communication but also suggest that even de-noised signal retain distortions that can be detrimental in conversational scenarios. These initial results, which we plan to complement with a more formal study in the future, underscore the significance of speech enhancement in virtual reality interactions and demonstrate how VR can be used to evaluate novel audio processing algorithms.

In recent years, assistive and multimedia technologies have advanced significantly, with many low-level challenges, such as denoising, nearly resolved. Consequently, the focus is shifting towards a broader, more integrative view of how users interact

with technology and each other (Pan and Hamilton, 2018; Billinghamurst et al., 2024). Developing new algorithms increasingly requires expertise from human-centered fields such as psychology and sociology (Gregori et al., 2023). This paper examines existing audio technology through the lens of human interactions and presents an original perspective on communication in XR, supporting a multidisciplinary approach in research and technology.

Data availability statement

The raw data supporting the conclusions of this article will be made available by the authors, without undue reservation.

Ethics statement

No ethical approval was required for studies involving human participants. All participants were informed about the content of the demonstration and agreed to participate, as well as to have their responses to the final survey used for the analysis presented in the article. The surveys were completely anonymous, and participants were informed that they could withdraw from the demonstration and the analysis at any time. No personal data of the participants was processed; only fully anonymized data was collected and handled. The studies were conducted in accordance with national legislation and institutional requirements. Written informed consent to participate was not required from participants or their legal guardians/family members, in accordance with national legislation and institutional requirements, as no personal data of the participants was collected at any point. The participants consented to participate in the studies and agreed to complete the online form, being fully informed about the study, their rights, and the use of anonymized data to ensure confidentiality.

Author contributions

JL: Writing—original draft, Writing—review and editing. EG: Writing—review and editing. US: Writing—review and editing. AG: Writing—review and editing.

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